

Fluorinated indole derivatives : Synthetic and biomedical aspects

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A recent trend in indole chemistry is the incorporation of fluorine at an appropriate site to influence enzyme action and also to enhance lipid solubility. A brief review of the work done during the last four decades is presented.

Indole (1), along with its 2,3-dione derivative isatin (2), has been associated as a common denominator of psychotropism and several review articles^{1,2} have appeared on the medicinal uses of some well known indole derivatives like DMT, indomethacin, serotonin etc.

Indole is also a main constituent unit in most of the alkaloids such as psilobin, harmine, strychnine, monomeric and dimeric vinca, ibogo, aspidosperm etc.³.

Both the rings are reactive towards electrophilic substitution at 3-position. Apart from this, there is an active hydrogen atom attached to nitrogen and an aromatic ring which should substitute at 5- and 7-positions. Introduction of substituents at 5- or 6-positions of the indole ring is expected to prevent enzymatic hydroxylation and conjugation.

In the late 1940s, investigations by Rudolf Peters into the biochemistry of C-F bond established the concept of lethal synthesis. The introduction of fluorine into pharmaceuticals brought about a revolution in the 1950s. Incorporation of fluorine into the indole nucleus is reported to increase drug persistence by increasing its solubility in lipid material and fat deposits in body⁴ and cause changes in the biological activities.

This review article attempts to cover all types of indole derivatives, with an appropriate fluorine substituent. More emphasis has been placed on compounds with medicinal properties. The text has been classified in terms of (i) simple indole derivatives, (ii) condensed systems and (iii) spiroindole derivatives. Wherever possible, brief synthetic details and biological properties are given. A detailed description will be beyond the scope of this review.

Simple indole derivatives

Tryptamine derivatives :

Tryptamine (3; 3- β -aminoethylindole) is well known for

its antiserotonin, adrenergic, psychotic, dopadecarboxylase inhibition etc. activities². Structure-activity relationship of tryptamine derivatives and their effect on spinal reflexes have been described⁵.

Some 4-, 5-, or 6-fluoro- and 4-trifluoromethyl analogs (4) of tryptamine have been prepared and screened for CNS activity⁶. 5-Fluorotryptamine was found more active than 4- and 6- analogs⁷.

Fluorine containing 3-indolyglyoxamides and tryptamines were prepared by treating the appropriate indolyglyoxal chloride with $\text{HN}(\text{R}^1)(\text{R}^2)$ and were then reduced with LiAlH_4 to yield compounds of the type 5^{8,9}.

X = CH₂CH₂
R = 5-F, 6-F
R₁ = H, F
R₂ = Me, Et

3-Substituted 1-(4-fluorophenyl)-1H-indoles :

While investigating D-2 and 5-HT₂ antagonists, Perregaard *et al.*¹⁰ prepared a series of 1-[1-(4-fluorophenyl)-1H-indol-3-yl]piperazines (6).

All the compounds displayed dopamine D-2 and serotonin

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5-HT₂ receptor properties.

2-(4-Fluorophenyl)indoles were subjected to Mannich reaction with 1-arylpiperazines to give compounds of the type 7 as possible psychopharmacological agents¹¹.

R = H, 4-F, 3-CF₃, 4-Cl
X = CO

Acidic derivatives of indole :

Fluorinated indoleacetic acid derivatives have been prepared as antiinflammatory drugs¹². A solution of 1-(4-fluorobenzoyl)-5-methoxy-2-methyl-1*H*-indole-3-acetic acid and benzoyl oxycarbonylmethyl ester in ethyl acetate was hydrogenated over Pd/C to give 8.

R = F, Cl,
3-perfluoroalkyl

6-Fluoro-2-methyl-3-indolepropionic acid has been patented in 1974¹³. Several β-indole butyric acid derivatives have been investigated for their plant growth regulator activities¹⁴. These include 4,4,4,-trifluoro-3-(indole-3-)butyric acid.

R = H, OH
R¹ = COOH, Cyano

The title compounds (9) were prepared by stirring diethyl malonate with Na in Ph.Me and treating with 2,2,2-trifluoro-1-(3-indolyl)ethanol under reflux and subsequently decarboxylated with aq. K₂CO₃ in MeOH¹⁵. This group has also reported several other studies on the subject¹⁶ and many of these are patented. A series of *N*-trifluoroacetyl/pentafluoropropionyl-*O*-trifluoroethyl/pentafluoropropyl/heptafluorobutyl ester derivatives of 5-methoxyindole-3-acetic acid (5 MIAA) have been synthesized¹⁷ and their electron capture negative ionization mass spectrometry studied. Various fluorinated 3-indolylimines, on stirring at room temperature with mercaptoacetic acid/mercaptopropionic acid gave [2,3-dihydro-3-phenyl-2-oxo-1*H*-indol-3-yl]thioethanoic acid¹⁸ (10).

(10)

6,6,6-Trifluoro-5-(indol-3-yl)-4-thiahexanoic acid derivatives (11) have been prepared¹⁹ as plant-growth regulators by heating 2,2,2-trifluoro-1-(indole-3)ethanol and HS.CH₂-CH₂COOH at 100° for 6 h.

R = H, lower alkyl
X = Halo
m = 1-3
n = 1,2

Potential biologically active indole derivatives

A series of fluorinated 3-[3-(piperidin-1-yl)propyl]indoles were developed as selective 5-HT_{1D} agonists²⁰. Fluorinated indole derivatives of the type 12 have been synthesized for studying their affinity for the cannabinoid receptor activity²¹.

R¹ = H, lower alkyl, aryl benzyl
R²-R⁴ = H, lower alkyl, lower fluorinated alkyl, halogen
R⁷ = H, lower alkyl
Q¹ = H, CHO, CN
Q² = Ph, naphthyl

Fluorine-containing indoles of the type (13) have been investigated as tillering promoters for gramineous plants²².

R¹, R² = H, alkyl
Y = alkoxy, NH₂

A series of fluorinated 3-benzyl-5-indolecarboxyamides have been reported as orally active antagonists of leukotrienes D₄ and E₄²³.

New indolactam derivatives, with a F atom at position 5 or 6 were synthesized (14) as tumor promoter teleocidins²⁴. It was noticed that (-)-5-fluoroindolactom-v (I), existing mainly as the sofa conformer, was far less biologically active than (-)-6-fluoroindolactam-v (II) existing mainly as the twist conformer.

Fluorine-containing 2-aryl-3-pyrazolyl/pyranyl/isooxazo-lynylindole derivatives (15) have been prepared as antifungal and antibacterial agents²⁵.

Some new fluorine-containing 2-{[2-(fluoroaryl)-1*H*-in-

dole-3-yl]methylene}hydrazine carbothioamides and carboxal-dehydes (16) were prepared for their possible antifertility activity²⁶.

(16)

Fluorinated derivatives of 3-phenyl iminoindol 2(3*H*)-one (17) were tested for their antimicrobial activities against bacteria and fungi²⁷.

(17)

Fluorine-containing 3-substituted-indole-2-ones (18) were prepared²⁸ for studying their C.N.S. activity, viz. analgesic, anticonvulsant and effects against amphetamine-induced stereotypy and on potentiation of pentobarbitone Na hypnosis.

(18)

Some new fluorine-containing indole-2,3-dione derivatives were prepared including aminoacetyl indole-diones (19) and compounds of the type 20 and were found to inhibit *Staphylococcus albus* and *Escherichia coli*²⁹

(19)

(20)

Various fluorine containing indole derivatives with substituents at 2, 3 and 5 positions were prepared (21) to study their antibacterial activity³⁰.

(21)

In addition, in another type of compounds with a different set of substituents (22), some possible psychopharmacological agents were obtained³¹.

(22)

Polyfluorinated indole derivatives :

We have reported the synthesis of 2-pentafluorophenyl-5/6-fluoroindoles (23) and their various derivatives. The presence of several F atoms may impart novel biological properties to the compounds³².

(23)

Kobayashi *et al.*³³ reported the synthesis and reactions of trifluoromethylindoles from 3- and 4-(trifluoromethyl) quinoline. Chemistry of 4,5,6,7-tetrafluoroindoles has been studied extensively³⁴ but the details are not available. Brooke *et al.*³⁵ synthesized a series of *N*-phenyl-4,5,6,7-tetrafluoro-2-phenylindoles by a new cyclization reaction and attempted synthesis of related compounds. *N*-Phenyl-4,5,6,7-tetrafluoro-2-phenylindole was prepared by the reaction of phenyl 2,3,4,5,6-pentafluorobenzyl ketone with aniline. 4,5,6,7-Tetrafluorotryptophan, 4,5,6,7-tetrafluoroheteroauxin and 4,5,6,7-tetrafluorotryptamine were prepared³⁶ from 4,5,6,7-tetrafluoro-3-(piperidinomethyl)indole and dimethyl sulfate as starting materials and subsequent hydrolysis of the diester.

The pentafluorophenyl- and 1,3,4,5,5,6,7,8-heptafluoro-

2-naphthylhydrazones of a variety of aldehydes and ketones give 4,5,6,7-tetrafluoroindole and 4,5,6,7,8,9-hexafluoro-benz(e)indole derivatives when heated under reflux in tetralin³⁷. These products (24) are typical Fischer indole products, yet the substrates all have F in positions *ortho* to N rather than H.

R = Me, Et, CH₂Ph
R' = Me, Ph, H, 4-Me C₆H₄

Such reactions were further investigated using RNH.N : CMePh (R = heptafluoro-2-naphthyl and R = C₆F₅) and products of the types 25-27 were obtained³⁸. These are typical Fischer indole products but are formed by displacement of *ortho* F and not *ortho* H.

Miscellaneous indole derivatives :

New indolactam derivatives (28) with a F, Br, I or Me group at position 6 of indolactam-V were synthesized by microbial conversion using *Streptovercillum blastomy-cetium* NA 34-17³⁹.

R = F, Br, I, Me

Some new fluorinated indoles have been prepared through pyridinium ylides⁴⁰ by cyclocondensations of

phenacylpyridinium bromides with appropriate amines. Barton *et al*⁴¹ reported fluorination of benzofuran and *N*-acylindoles with trifluoroxymethane.

Spectral studies :

The ¹³C and ¹H NMR spectra of monofluorotryptophans and difluorotryptophans in CD₃OD were assigned based on 1- and 2-D NMR techniques. Fluorine substituent effects on the chemical shifts of tryptophan were calculated and compared with those of indole⁴².

The mass fragmentation pathways of some fluorine containing indoles like 5-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indole were studied and structural assignments made for the major fragments and the pathways leading to their formulation postulated by the recognition of appropriate metastable peaks and doubly charged ions⁴³

Mass spectral studies of some other fluorinated indoles and benzindoles have also been reported⁴⁴. Fluorinated indoles having a Me group in the 5-position show a similar fragmentation pattern while in the case of 7-ethoxyindoles, the initial fragmentation occurs around EtO group.

Condensed indole derivatives

A number of polymembered indole derivatives were synthesized from isatin which is indole-2,3-dione. It is a unique molecule possessing both amide and ketocarbonyl group and exists in tautomeric forms (29a, 29b).

The C-3 carbonyl group of isatin is strongly electrophilic. Isatins, therefore, are readily involved in condensation and addition reactions. In general, there are three possibilities during condensation reactions : (i) both the α,β -carbonyl groups, having varying reactivity are involved, (ii) ring cleavage takes place and (iii) ring expansion occurs. It has been generally observed that nature of the final product always depends on the experimental conditions and substituents at nitrogen atom which may affect the electron density of α - and β -carbonyl carbon atom respectively⁴⁵.

Triazino[5,6-b]indole :

A series of new fluorine-containing 3-dialkylaminoethylthio-5-morpholinomethyl-[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles (30) have been synthesized⁴⁶ and screened for bactericidal, fungicidal and virucidal activities.

Similarly, closely related compounds of the type 31 were found to be useful as bactericides⁴⁷.

Some controversy was noticed about the structure of the final product when 3-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazines were cyclized with nitrous acid⁴⁸. Therefore, the reaction of 3-hydrazino-

1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole with nitrous acid was reinvestigated and a novel tetracyclic ring system, 10*H*-tetrazolo[5',1':3,4][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indole (32) was obtained.

The reaction of 3-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazinoindoles with various reagents, was further investigated with ethyl acetoacetate which had not been studied earlier⁴⁹. Novel tetracyclic ring systems, having angular (33) and linear (34) structures were synthesized.

In yet another study, it was found that when the reaction was done in carbon disulfide, 2,3-dihydro-1-thioxo-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*c*]-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles (35) was obtained⁵⁰

Some 3-arylthiazolo[3,2:2',8']-1,2,4-triazino[5',6'-*b*]indoles

(36) have also been obtained using H₃PO₃ for cyclization⁵¹.

*Indolo[2,3-*a*]carbazoles and acridines :*

Fluorinated trifluoromethylated indolo[2,3-*a*]carbazoles (37) and indolo[2,3-*a*]acridines (38) have been prepared by Fischer-indole synthesis of oxotetrahydrocarbazoles with PhNHNH₂ as potential carcinogenic compounds⁵².

Benzindoles :

Some new fluorinated indoles and benzindoles have also been synthesized through pyridinium ylides⁵³. Cyclocondensation atom of phenacylpyridinium bromides with 1- and 2-naphthylamine gave 39 and 40, respectively.

Synthetic and mechanistic studies have been made on highly fluorinated benzindole derivatives. A plausible mechanism has been given for the formation of the Fischer-indole product from acetophenone 1,3,4,5,6,7,8-heptafluoro-2-naphthylhydrazone in which *o*-fluorine is lost (41)⁵⁴

Aromatic nucleophilic nitrogen-nitrogen exchange reaction of *N,N*-dimethyl-2,4-bis(trifluoroacetyl)-1-naphthylamine with amino acid derivatives have been studied and a facile synthesis of fluorine-containing 1*H*-benzo[*g*]indolines and

1*H*-benzo[*g*]indoles (42) accomplished⁵⁵

(42)

R² = H, Me

Pyrazolo[3',4'.5,6]pyridazino[3,4-b]indole :

The reaction of fluorine-containing indolones with phenylhydrazine in absolute ethanol and glacial acetic acid was studied⁵⁶. It was found that while a spiro compound (43) was obtained in absolute alcohol, in glacial acetic acid, a fused tetracyclic product (44) was obtained besides other products. With hydrazine hydrate also, a mixture of spiro and fused tetracyclic products were obtained.

(43)

R¹ = H, COCH₃
X = 5F, 6F

(44)

1,3-Diazepino[4,5-b]indoles :

The reactions of fluorinated 3-*aroyl*-methyleneindol-2-ones with thiourea and phenylthiourea were investigated^{57,58}. An interesting observation was made that while thiourea gave a novel indole system 1,3-diazepino[4,5-*b*]indole-2-thione (45), under exactly similar conditions, thiourea gave a spiro compound, spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(3'*H*)-pyrimidin]-2(1*H*)-one (46).

(45)

(46)

Pyridazino[3,4-b]indoles :

The reaction of 3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethylidene)-2*H*-indol-2-one with various hydrazines similarly gives a mixture of products⁵⁹ including pyridazino[3,4-*b*]indole derivatives (47). Various hydrazine derivatives such as phenylhydrazine and pentafluorophenylhydrazine may alter the course of reaction. In a study of this reaction with phenylhydrazine in

glacial acetic acid, a spiro compound, a hydrazone and a pyridazino[3,4-*b*]indole derivative were obtained (47).

(47)

R¹ = H
R² = C₆H₅

Pyrazoloazepino[4,5-b]indoles :

An interesting reaction was noticed when fluorinated 1,3-dihydro-3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethylidene)indol-2-(*H*)-ones were allowed to react with 3-aminopyrazolone in absolute alcohol. Besides other products like a spiro compound⁶⁰, a pyrazolo[3',4':2,3]azepino[4,5-*b*]indol-1(2*H*)-one (48) was isolated.

(48)

Indolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines :

Reactions of fluorine-containing indole-2,3-diones with fluorinated 1,2-phenylenediamines have been investigated in different media⁶¹. In glacial acetic acid, indolo[2,3-*b*]quinoxalines were obtained exclusively (49). The compounds were screened for their action on the central nervous system.

(49)

R = H, F, CF₃
R¹ = H, 4-F, 5-F, 3-CF₃

*Indolo[2,3-e]dibenzo[*b,h*][1,4,7]oxadiazonines :*

The reaction products of ketones and 2-aminophenols have many biological and industrial applications⁶². Fluorine incorporation in heterocycles is known to effect the course of reaction besides influencing the biological activity. Prompted by this, the reaction of fluorinated isatin derivatives with 2-aminophenol was investigated and a novel pentacyclic ring system, indolo[2,3-*e*]dibenzo[*b,h*][1,4,7]-oxadiazonine (50) was obtained besides some other products.

Imidazo[4,5-b]indoles :

Direct condensation of indole-2,3-diones with aromatic

(50)
 $R^1 = 5F, 6F$
 $R = H, COCH_3$

aldehydes in the presence of an excess of ammonium acetate in acidic medium yielded 2-aryl-1*H*-imidazo[4,5-*b*]indoles (51)⁶³

(51)
 $R^1 = 5-F, 6-F$
 $R = C_6H_5, -C_6H_4Cl$

Indoles with C-3 as spiro atom

As mentioned earlier, the C-3 carbonyl group of isatin is strongly electrophilic and thus isatins are involved in condensation and addition reactions with carbanion type nucleophiles. Many of these reactions lead to the synthesis of spiroindoles with C-3 as spiro atom. The C-3 atom of the indole ring is shared with another ring and leads to a variety of heterocyclic systems attached at C-3 of the indole ring.

In our extensive work on fluorinated isatins and consequent spiro systems, we have been able to incorporate various kinds of rings beginning from a one-ring system (with or without a heteroatom) like cyclopropane to three-ring systems with heteroatoms and have reported some very interesting new ring systems. Most of this work is already published and we have given a detailed account of our work in two review articles^{64,65}. We therefore do not propose to give these details in the present article to avoid repetitions. However, it will be pertinent to outline here the systems reported for ready reference and the reader is advised to refer to the earlier references⁶⁵ for details.

Majority of these compounds have a fluorine substituent at an appropriate site. Introduction of fluorine into the indole nucleus is believed to increase drug persistence by increasing its solubility in lipid material and fat deposits in body⁴. The chemotherapeutic importance of fluorinated isatin derivatives is well established. These appropriately substituted isatins have been exploited for synthesizing several new heterocyclic systems which have been reported for the first time. Some more important spiroheterocycles reported by us during the last two decades are as follows :

spiro[indole-thiazolidine]ones, spiro[indole-pyrazole]ones, spiro[indoline-pyrazolopyridines], spiro[pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles], spiro[pyrazolo[3,4-*c*]pyrazoles], spiro[indole-pyrimidines], spiro[indole-thiazines], spiro[indole-isoxazoles], spiro[indole-oxiranes], spiro[benzopyran-indoles], spiro[benzothiazine-indoles], spiro[indole-tetrazine]thiones, spiro[acridine-indoles], spiro[azetidine-indoles], spiro[indole-pyrano][2,3-*d*]pyrimidines, spiro[benzimidazole-indoles], spiro[triazolo[5,1-*b*]quinazolines], spiro[indole-pyranobenzopyrans] and spiro[indeno-indoles]. The clinical studies of a limited number of compounds have also been carried out.

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References

1. V. M. Sim, *J. Forensic Sci.*, 1961, 6, 39.
2. K. C. Joshi and P. Chand, *Pharmazie*, 1982, 37, 1, and references therein.
3. R. J. Sundberg, "The Chemistry of Indoles", Academic, New York, 1970.
4. B. A. Whittee and E. H. P. Young, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1963, 6, 378.
5. T. Marezynoki, *Pharmacol.*, 1962, 14, 247.
6. P. Alfred, Ger. Pat. 2337461/1975 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, 82, 156069).
7. A. Kalir and Balderman, *Israel J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 927.
8. K. C. Joshi, V. N. Pathak and P. Chand, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1978, 42, 1723.
9. K. C. Joshi, V. N. Pathak and R. Pal, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1980, 111, 1343.
10. J. Perregaard, J. Arnt, P. Bogeso, J. Hyhel and C. Sanchez, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1992, 35, 1092.
11. K. C. Joshi, V. N. Pathak and P. Chand, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 423.
12. C. Fukaya, Y. Naito, S. Hanada, M. Watanbe and K. Yokoyama, US Pat. 4868201.
13. K. Sasajima, Jap. Pat. JP 71-24373 710415/1974.
14. K. Kato, M. Katayama, H. Kimoto, R. K. Gautam and Y. Kamuro, *Nogoya Kogyo Gijutsu Shikensho Hokoku*, 1993, 42, 215.
15. M. Katayama, S. Fujii, N. Kimoto and A. Shida, Jap. Pat. JP 91-54864 910319/1993.
16. M. Katayama, K. Kato, H. Kimoto and S. Fuji, *Jap. Experientia*, 1995, 51, 721.
17. P. Li, K. L. Wong, C. Y. Miranda, C. W. Tsang and S. F. Pand, *J. Mass Spectrom.*, 1996, 31, 1228.

18. A. Dandia, M. Saha, A. Shivpuri and V. Sehgal, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1997, **9**, 804.
19. M. Katayama, S. Fujii, H. Kimoto and A. Shida, *Jap. Pat.* 91-198880 9107 12/1992
20. J. L. Castro I. Collins, R. Ian, G. N. Michael, A. P. Watt and B. Sohal, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1998, **41**, 2667.
21. M. Gallant, Y. Gareau, D. Guay, L. Danil, M. Labelle and P. Marc, *US Pat.* 95-388929 950215/1996.
22. M. Katayama, S. Fujii, K. Kato and H. Kimoto, *Jap. Pat.* JP 94-84 123 940329/1996.
23. R. T. Jacobs, P. R. Bernstein, L. A. Cronk, E. P. Vacek, L. F. Newcomb, D. Aharony, C. K. Buckner and E. J. Kusner, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1994, **37**, 1282
24. S. Okuno, K. Irie, Y. Suzuki, K. Kohimizu and I. Hoyoku, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 1994, **4**, 431.
25. A. Dandia, V. Sehgal and P. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1993, **32**, 1288.
26. K. C. Joshi, V. N. Pathak and R. K. Chaturvedi, *Pharmazie*, 1986, **41**, 634
27. E. Piscopo, M. V. Diurno, M. Antonucci, M. Imperadrice, F. Calundo and V. Cataldi, *Boll. Soc. Ital. Biol. Sper.*, 1985, **61**, 1327.
28. K. C. Joshi, R. Patni, P. Chand, V. Sharma, S. K. Bhattacharya and S. K. Rao, *Pharmazie*, 1984, **39**, 153.
29. K. C. Joshi, V. N. Pathak and S. K. Jain, *Pharmazie*, 1980, **35**, 677
30. K. C. Joshi, V. N. Pathak, P. Arya and P. Chand, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1979, **43**, 171.
31. K. C. Joshi, V. N. Pathak and P. Chand, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1978, **320**, 701.
32. V. N. Pathak, R. Joshi, R. K. Chaturvedi and R. Pathak, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1996, **5**, 177.
33. Y. Kohayashi, I. Kumadoki, Y. Hirose and H. Yoshibumi, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1974, **39**, 1836.
34. S. Woods, Dissertation, I.I.T., Chicago, 1973.
35. G. M. Brooke, W. K. R. Musgrave, R. J. D. Rutherford and T. W. Smith, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, **27**, 5653.
36. T. D. Petrova, T. I. Savchenko, T. F. Ardyukova and G. G. Y. Khim, *Geterotsike Soedin.*, 1971, **7**, 213.
37. D. F. Benke and G. M. Brooke, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 1984, **26**, 77
38. G. M. Brooke, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1983, 821.
39. K. Irie, M. Iguchi, T. Oda, Y. Suzuki, S. Okuno, H. Ohigashi, K. Koshimizu, H. Hayashi and M. Arai, *Tetrahedron*, 1995, **51**, 6255
40. R. K. Bansal and G. Bhagchandani, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, **19**, 801.
41. D. H. R. Barton, R. H. Hesse and G. P. Jackman, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1977, 2604.
42. M. Lee and R. S. Phillips, *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 1992, **30**, 1035.
43. K. C. Joshi, V. N. Pathak and P. Chand, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 111.
44. R. K. Bansal, G. Bhagchandani, S. Mathur and U. C. Pande, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 850.
45. A. V. N. Chenko, A. G. Drushlyak and V. V. Tatov, *Chem. Heterocycl. Comp.*, 1984, **10**, 1155.
46. K. C. Joshi, V. N. Pathak and S. K. Jain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 1176
47. K. C. Joshi and S. K. Jain, *Curr. Sci.*, 1982, **51**, 346
48. K. C. Joshi and P. Chand, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1980, **17**, 1783
49. K. C. Joshi, A. Dandia and S. Baweja, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1989, **26**, 545.
50. K. C. Joshi, A. Dandia and S. Baweja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 690.
51. K. C. Joshi, V. N. Pathak and S. K. Jain, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1981, 159.
52. A. Stroppaghetti, G. Rabere, A. Fravolini and P. Jacquignon, *Heterocycles*, 1980, **14**, 935
53. R. K. Bansal and G. Bhagchandani, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, **19**, 801.
54. G. M. Brooke, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 1988, **40**, 51.
55. M. Hojo, R. Masuda, E. Oroda and M. Hiroshi, *Synthesis*, 1989, **7**, 550.
56. K. C. Joshi, A. Dandia, C. S. Sharma and R. Joshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 459
57. K. C. Joshi, R. Jain and S. Arora, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1990, **29**, 369
58. A. Dandia and A. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **72**, 833.
59. K. C. Joshi, A. Dandia and S. Bhagat, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1992, **31**, 98.
60. K. C. Joshi, A. Dandia and S. Khanna, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1990, **29**, 933.
61. K. C. Joshi, P. Chand and A. Dandia, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, **23**, 743.
62. A. Dandia, S. Khanna and K. C. Joshi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1991, **30**, 468.
63. A. Dandia and A. Gupta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1994, **33**, 1093.
64. K. C. Joshi, R. Jain and P. Chand, *Heterocycles*, 1985, **23**, 957.
65. K. C. Joshi and R. Joshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 643, and the references cited therein.